

The micro-macro interfaces of higher education, innovation, regional growth and regional development.

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Introduction

Current public debates about the costs and benefits of universities, and the roles they should play in today's and tomorrow's world often include references to broad, and sometimes challenging economic notions such as human capital, technological progress, patents, innovation, globalization and knowledge economy. It is true that universities located in different regions or countries may differ among them in many dimensions because of a number of reasons, including historical causes, institutional arrangements, and financial support. Nonetheless, all of them share a common key aspect, as they are institutions of higher education, which implies the fact that some individuals enroll in as freshmen, progress through as students linked to particular study programmes, and will later leave the institution, either as graduates or as dropouts. The factual sequence happens term after term and has been happening for years or decades, even for centuries in the case of some institutions. For those who take part in as students, the outcome of the university education process has direct consequences that reach a variety of personal dimensions including, but not limited to, wealthier economic prospects, as graduation from university open access to better job opportunities, and reduces the risks of unemployment. Additionally, personal employment status is an essential factor in the distribution of aggregate income among individuals and groups. In that way, every term new cohorts of students enroll and new cohorts of graduates leave universities to develop their personal trajectories and professional careers in a diversity of positions and domains to achieve their material and personal objectives. The consequence is that the long-term impact of universities, transmitted through successive overlapping cohorts of graduates, will influence significantly the evolution of the economy, the democratic system, and the territory over time, thus influencing the living conditions available to future generations. Therefore, current university practice,

that is, the strategies that universities follow to help prepare students for their lives and careers as graduates, are relevant issues for a variety of stakeholders, including students and their families, faculty, university managers, business managers, other potential employers, and regional and national governments.

Typically, researchers in social and behavioral sciences address the role of universities either from agent-based micro approaches or from aggregate-based macro approaches. Economists, in particular, focus their microeconomic analyses on the behavior of individual agents in specific markets and settings, while their macroeconomic analyses take into consideration the operation of economic systems as a whole at a chosen level of aggregation, such as industry, region, or country levels. Most of the analyses seek to examine the likelihood of causal processes between observable phenomena, and researchers usually conceptualize those processes in terms of impulse-response, or input-output relationships linking theoretical constructs, in order to obtain a view of the relative effects of diverse impulses or input concepts explaining differences in responses or output concepts. When the output from one process enters as an input in a different process, examination of long chains of impulse-response relationships becomes possible. However, the theoretical concepts involved in those relationships are often measured through the observation of phenomena that happen at aggregation levels different from the one in which the relationship is conceptualized. Moreover, every impulse-response process between two constructs conceptualized at a given level of aggregation may interact significantly with other processes that in turn may take place at the same or at different level of analysis.

Micro-macro interfaces encompass the systems of interactions that exist at diverse levels of aggregation between the concepts and processes involved in a causal relationship or chain of relationships, and between the hypothesized causal relationships themselves. In the case of the links between university education as impulse concept and regional development as response concept, the micro-macro interfaces refer in general to the systems of interactions that rule a variety of individual efforts into diverse types of output at organization level, and those organizational outputs, in turn, into aggregate economic and societal outcomes at regional level. Sometimes, researchers are able to take into consideration the presence of such micro-

macro interfaces explicitly by adding extra parameters or equations to the model specified to represent a particular relationship within a given level of analysis. Other times, the influence of micro-macro interfaces is discussed only in qualitative terms, in order to derive practice or policy implications from otherwise quantitative analyses; most often, however, the role of micro-macro interfaces is just ignored in empirical research.

The chapter highlights the influence of some of those micro-macro interfaces at regional level regarding university education impulse on the path towards regional development and well-being as response. Clarification of the issue involves discussion on the economic functions of knowledge in its diverse forms by bringing together theory, research and practice from at least four scientific domains. From education science, the central idea is that people change as they learn, and differentiate as they develop diverse activities and capacities. From economics, the key notion is that educated people contribute more than other people do to private and public wellbeing. From management science, the key idea is that good decisions at any level of an organization have practical impacts driving change in the real world. Finally, from regional science, the premise is that territories and societies reflect the consequences of local people's activities over time.

Within the framework defined by these four notions, the chapter is organized as follows. The second section briefly overviews the evolution of the two key concepts that economic rationality uses to link the activities of universities and the development of territories and societies, human capital and technological progress, from the original views of pre-classical and classical economists to the contemporary conceptions inspiring recent empirical research on regional economic growth. Section three focus on two types of micro-macro interfaces that arise in aggregate analyses on the role of universities for regional economic development, particularly those related to the influence of local systems and contexts, and those linked to the presence of knowledge-related spillovers at the regional level. Section four, in turn, focus on the micro-macro interfaces present in the transition of individual graduates from university education to post-graduate positions and careers within work organizations. The transition is conceptualized as a sequence of five partial impulse-response relationships linking an

initial university impulse to a response in terms of graduate performance at work a number of years after graduation. The section also describes two pieces of research as examples of how the interactions between individuals and organizations may influence the transmission of impulses through the diverse steps of the transition process. The first example focus on the process of education production with the development of competencies for innovation as output, while the second connects education production with subsequent graduate job behavior regarding leadership functions using individual competency profiles for leadership as inter-temporal connector. Finally, section five concludes with a summary of the key points on micro-macro interfaces and some implications of the analysis for diverse types of actors involved in the causal relationship between university education and economic development.

Human capital, technological progress and the economy

From aggregate, macro perspectives, economists have discussed extensively the mechanisms that explain the effects of higher education investments on economic growth. Macro-economic analysis highlights two essential functions that universities perform to fuel aggregate material prosperity at regional or national level. The first one is that universities, as educational institutions, contribute as sources of human capital; the second function is that their research activities generate most of the novel ideas shaping technological progress. Both elements, human capital and technological progress are arguments of the aggregate production function of the economy, and foster in turn future productivity gains for the whole economy and its members.

The positive effects of universities are empirically accounted for in terms of output growth rates, which are defined and calculated at relevant levels of aggregation, such as industry, region or country levels. Clearly, such approaches are only partial, since output growth and economic development are rather different concepts, and the respective terms should not be used as interchangeable in the public debate, because the concept of development always includes consideration of two objectives that are absent in mainstream growth analysis. The first one is improving the environmental sustainability of the production and consumption systems; the second one is the advance towards fairer schemas in the distribution of aggregate income. Moreover, the social non-monetary returns to education investment include a wide range of gains for society as a

whole that arise directly from the promotion of better educational opportunities for more inclusive social groups, and some of these benefits are perceived only in terms of fewer inequalities in the distribution of aggregate national or regional wealth. University education reduces the risks of poverty and social alienation because graduates are less likely to be left behind in the process of development, as they enjoy better job opportunities; besides, the incidence and duration of unemployment are generally lower amongst higher education graduates than amongst individuals with lower levels of education. Consequently, university education contributes to the reduction of the average rates of dependency on income transfers and other subsidies, and to reduce social inequalities, although that would only happen, as Levin and Kelley (1991) point out, if the production system is able at the same time to generate enough suitable employment opportunities for university graduates.

Universities contribute to aggregate human capital accumulation in the economy by pursuing their first mission, teaching students. To accomplish the mission, universities perform a wide variety of educational activities that would ultimately transform students into university graduates, thus increasing the aggregate stock of human capital available to the production sectors. The process of transformation takes several years during which both universities and students merge their resources and efforts in a production process that combines material and human resources to generate a valuable output in the form of a flow of university-educated people ready to contribute to aggregate production. The second mission of universities, research, is another production process essentially targeted at the generation, discussion and evaluation of novel ideas and new knowledge. The third mission of universities, knowledge transfer, is the process whereby a flow of potentially useful new knowledge and ideas, the kernel for technological and organizational change in the economy made available to business and other organizations actually producing consumption goods and services to satisfy human needs.

Generically, the concept of human capital refers to the value of people's productive skills, and grounds on the realization that individuals decide to invest part of their own resources in improving their own productive capacities with the expectation of reaping greater future returns. Theodor Schultz was the first economist to coin the term "human

capital" in 1959 with the intention of emphasizing the relevance that the improvement of people's education had had on the path of economic growth in the USA during the first half of the twentieth century. The notion that people may and should enhance their own productive value at a cost is, however, one of the oldest in economic science. Historically, William Petty was the first pre-classical economist to raise the idea that people have an economic value proportional to their income, and proposed to calculate the productive value of a worker by multiplying one year income by a factor of 20. Later, Adam Smith explicitly recommended the development of skills and abilities of the nation's population after observing that the benefits generated more than compensate the resources required for improving people's productive capacities. However, he was critical with public schools, and suggested that private schools where students pay for the teachers' salaries were preferable to stimulate competition among schools, thus contributing to raising the quality of education and the overall efficiency of the system. In nineteenth century, John Stuart Mill included the qualifications of the workforce as a crucial part of national wealth, although, unlike Smith, pointed out that in the field of education, market mechanisms did not work effectively since those demanding education services were not competent enough to judge its quality because they rely on incomplete information. Although there are hardly any explicit references to education or human capital in Karl Marx, he made a key contribution when he highlighted that skilled labor had more productive value than unskilled labor, and that individuals may obtain qualifications through additional efforts in their own education. The idea of qualifications as a product obtained by means of education will be taken up much later by economists alien to the Marxist thought to develop formally the notion of human capital. Despite the rich classical background, the neoclassical school of thought did not pay much attention to the productive value of the people and excluded, in general, the concept of an education-build human capital from the definition of wealth and capital in the broad sense until the second half of the twentieth century, when the contributions of Theodor Schultz and Gary Becker triggered the development of the human capital paradigm. Under that view, working people contribute to the production system not only their capacity for effort and dedication, but also their natural, born talents plus a set of knowledge and skills that they develop through the investment in formal education and by gaining in time broader work and life experience. Currently, the

concept of human capital is a fundamental instrument for the analysis of productivity from both micro and macro perspectives. Micro perspectives include determination of optimal investment in education, estimation of educational rates of return, mobility in the labor market, study of wage differences, etc.; and macro perspectives include generation of technological change, temporary and spatial diffusion of innovation, disparities on economic growth path and in economic development, etc. It should be noted, however, that the term "human capital" serves in contemporary literature as an umbrella to shelter a diversity of economic concepts that are relevant at individual and aggregate levels. There are at least two main senses for the term human capital in economic analysis, as Hartog (2001) points out: a restrictive one, which includes only the value of the productive capacities acquired by individuals at a cost, and a wider one, which includes the costs of all human activities undertaken with the intention to increase future well-being. In that wider sense, people invest in human capital when, for example, they decide to raise expenditure on health services, spend more time looking for information on better paid jobs, accept jobs with low initial remuneration but good learning prospects, or emigrate in search of better opportunities. Aggregate analyses of the economic role of universities often take into consideration human capital in its more restrictive sense, and quantify its value through observables such as the average number of education years per worker, or the share of university graduates in the workforce.

A review of the literature suggests that there have been three main stages of development in the understanding of the effects of the activities of universities on aggregate economic performance. The first one follows the incorporation of human capital, the product of education, as an explicit input factor into the aggregate production function of the economy along with labor and capital stock. The second stage of development involves the analysis of the innovation process related to the endogenous generation of technological change, leading to the development of endogenous growth models (EGM). The third stage of development is the consideration of diverse types of knowledge-related external effects in the economy at diverse levels of aggregation. By bringing together human capital theory and neo-classical growth theory, new growth theory establishes a richer conceptual framework to understand how universities are able to generate positive effects on aggregate efficiency, economic

growth and human wellbeing. On the one hand, neo-classical growth theory describes a firm's output as a function of two factor inputs, capital and labor, with knowledge operating typically as an exogenous force enhancing labor effectiveness. In particular, neo-classical growth theory assumes that technological progress is driven by a scientific process evolving independently from economic forces, and, consequently, long-run growth rates are determined exogenously, from outside the economic system (Solow 1956). Endogenous growth models argue that economic growth appears within the economic system, as a direct result of internal processes, and, therefore, considers technological progress as an endogenous argument, which has been addressed from various perspectives such as increasing returns to scale, capital and innovation externalities, learning by doing, human capital accumulation and research performance. On the other hand, human capital theory predicts that improved knowledge makes individuals more productive; hence, they will enjoy higher reflecting their increased addition to the aggregate output. Consequently, the enhancement of a nation's or a region's human capital will lead to economic growth by means of the development of new forms of technology and more effective and efficient means for organizing production. The first version of endogenous growth theory was the so-called AK theory (Romer 1986), which did not make an explicit distinction between capital accumulation and technological change. AK theory was followed by a second wave of endogenous growth theory, generally known as innovation-based growth theory, which recognizes that intellectual capital, the source of technological progress, is distinct from physical capital and human capital. Physical capital is accumulated through savings, while human capital is accumulated through education. Intellectual capital, however, is accumulated through innovation. The creation of new knowledge to fuel innovation in the economy requires resources to be specifically allocated to research activities whereby the new knowledge is generated. In other words, the creation of new knowledge should be incorporated as an endogenous determinant in economic growth models. A body of literature focused on the economics of innovation offers the means to treat the creation of new technological knowledge as endogenous. The most prevalent model of technological change is the so-called knowledge production function (KPF), where innovative activity is expressed as a function of R&D input, and human capital input. KPF approaches were originally applied to firms behavior (Griliches 1979), although their

application consistently produced stronger evidence at broader levels of aggregation such as industries, regions or countries, which suggested the presence of knowledge-related external effects related to the production of new knowledge. Consequently, EGM models incorporating KPF most often assume that existing knowledge is a non-rival, partially excludable good that may generate external effects at the appropriate aggregation level (Romer 1990). In other words, endogenous growth models focus on the process of knowledge assimilation and on the external effects related to the assimilation of knowledge among firms, regions or countries, while the literature on knowledge production emphasizes the role of inventive performance and the external effects associated to the production of new useful ideas and knowledge (Acs, Audretsch, Braunerhjelm and Carlsson 2012). The so-called 'innovation systems' approach to aggregate productivity gains adds to the understanding of innovation dynamics at the aggregate level by highlighting the crucial role of physical location for economic activities regarding innovative performance and productivity gains. According to this view, contextual conditions such as the institutional arrangements, the patterns of geographic specialization, local demographic structures, and other specific characteristics of territories exert a decisive influence both on the spatial distribution of inventive performance and on the path of knowledge dissemination across diverse territorial units. The reason is that endogenous technological change appears only as consequence of applying human and material resources within a specific framework defined by the interaction between the social and structural conditions prevalent in a given territory at a given time (Lundvall 1992). The main findings related to this approach highlight that the potential for innovation of diverse territories emerges mainly from individual and organizational interaction in terms of synergies and networks. The influence of technical agencies, research infrastructures, education and training systems, governance structures, and local innovation policies would help explaining differences in innovative performance, and therefore in material wellbeing of the population, among different regions and countries.

Invention, innovation, knowledge related spatial spillovers and regional contexts

New growth theory suggests that regional economic performance is likely to depend on two knowledge-related constructs: the amount of knowledge already accumulated in a

region, and the flow of new knowledge available to the region's agents. Contextual, region-specific conditions also play a role in explaining regional differences in productivity and wellbeing. Aggregate productivity gains at regional level emerges then from two connected dynamic systems, the one related to the production of goods and services, and the other referring to technological progress. Additionally, knowledge-related inter-regional external effects may appear both in the creation of new knowledge and in its applications to the production of goods and services, as people create and accumulate knowledge through a wide variety of activities including trial and error, formal education, on-the-job training, learning by doing, and scientific research, among others. Furthermore, the whole production system may be regarded as the material results of using a certain stock of previously achieved knowledge, since everything that forms the economy, such as processes, products, technology, infrastructures and organizations, all emerged from what people discovered, created, developed and built in the past. The distinction between the technological, or explicit, and the organizational, or tacit, components of knowledge in the economy is relevant at the regional level because the two components emerge largely from different types of activities, and are accumulated and accounted for in different ways. Technological or explicit knowledge emerges primarily from research and development activity, and it is accumulated in the economy as physical capital. Organizational, or tacit knowledge, exists in people's brains, and in organization's expertise, in the forms of human ability, ideas, skills, competence, know-how and networking; it is individually generated through formal education in interaction with work, business and general life experience, and is accumulated in the economy in the form of aggregate human capital. The amount of already existing knowledge, both in explicit form as physical capital, and in tacit form as human capital, that the economy is able to use is, in turn, an essential factor input for the development of new useful knowledge. Research and development activities and higher education activities create new knowledge based on already existing organizational and technological knowledge in use. The newly-achieved explicit knowledge will increase the amount of knowledge available for the future in two ways. First, it would be assimilated into the production process as productive innovation, thus increasing the amount of knowledge ready to be used; and second, recently achieved useful knowledge will be learned by students at universities and other education

institutions, thus increasing the flow of future tacit knowledge updates through improved quality of the human resources. Figure 1 illustrates the relationships between the operation of the invention and innovation systems of a hypothetically isolated economy.

Figure 1. Invention and innovation systems in a closed economic system

The internal effect of human capital is the direct, aggregative effect of the acquisition of human capital on productivity gains, whereas its external effect arises from an increased average level of human capital in the economy, as Doyle and Weale (1994) pointed out. Consequently, the human capital hypothesis integrates with economic growth theory in a way that takes into consideration both the internal and external effects of the investment in education on economic performance. Within that framework, it becomes clear that universities are not only sources for human capital, but also drivers for innovation at the regional level. The diffusion of innovation in a region relates as well to the availability of a workforce with a sufficient and up-to-date set of capacities (Knabb & Stoddard 2005; Škare 2011). In particular, universities impact regional productivity in several ways via the creation of new knowledge. First, in most regions and countries a substantial proportion of the effort in basic and applied research is done within higher education institutions. Second, the education system provides qualified labor that is

available to local industry and service sectors, including those who will develop careers in research and development activities in the region. Third, the flow of graduates emerging from universities brings in, along with other components of human capital, the specific capacity to disseminate innovative knowledge at the workplace in local firms and organizations. It should be noted that the capacity for innovation is not restricted only to entrepreneurs, firm managers, or to those working on R&D, as many other graduates are likely to have opportunities for using in their activities knowledge recently discovered by others, and to develop new ideas while performing their job tasks and responsibilities .

The availability of new knowledge induces changes in the production process leading to increases in the demand for diverse types of highly qualified labor at the region level. The distribution of those changes in time and space depend on the corresponding distribution of inventive effort, which, in turn, requires a sufficient supply of highly qualified individuals able to create new useful knowledge. Consequently, regional patterns of investment in the creation of new knowledge through research and higher education activities are likely to explain regional divergences in income and wellbeing (Bilbao-Osorio & Rodríguez-Pose 2004). Recent empirical research on regional innovation and productivity brings together the diverse approaches to knowledge creation and assimilation found in the literature in order to understand how the new knowledge emerges locally, and how it is locally applied to production leading to regional productivity gains. Within this line, Moreno, Paci, and Usai (2005) addressed the spatial distribution of innovative activities and the role of technological spillovers in the process of knowledge creation and diffusion among European regions. Their results highlight the relevance of internal regional factors, such as specific R&D effort and agglomeration economies, to explain innovative performance, along with knowledge-related spillovers in the generation of new knowledge from innovative activity performed in other regions. The evidence also suggests that spatial spillovers decay with distance, being mostly constrained by national borders, and that technological similarity between regions is relevant to explain how innovation disseminates at regional level. Under the premise that innovative activities and economic activities do not distribute randomly in the territory, Usai (2008) describes strong differences in inventive

performance across regions in OECD countries, and estimates a KPF model that includes as factor inputs human capital, R&D, agglomeration effects, country level characteristics and spatial correlation. Estimates confirm that a region's inventive performance is directly influenced by the availability of human capital and R&D capacity in the region, shows how inventory capacity concentrates in specific regions that also tend to cluster together, and provides empirical evidence of national innovation systems strongly influencing the institutional framework within which innovation appears and disseminates at regional level. Rodriguez-Pose and Crescenzi (2011) approach combines R&D, knowledge spillovers and innovation systems approaches in an EGM model build up under the assumption that regional growth models should include human capital as factor input in the production function starting the causal chain between research, innovation and growth. The empirical model includes knowledge-related external effects at regional level to complete the analysis of innovation systems territorially located, where endogenous technological change appears to be influenced by the contextual conditions prevalent in diverse regions. The results disclose how the interaction between local and external research, on the one hand, along with local and external socio-economic and institutional conditions, on the other hand, shape the capacity for innovation of regions, and also point out that spatial proximity plays a prominent role for the transmission of productive knowledge, as estimates of spatial knowledge spillovers decay rapidly with distance. All these contributions address the economic role of knowledge at regional level by means of single-equation models that combine diverse internal (human capital, R&D and social context) and external factors (diverse types of knowledge-related spatial spillovers) that interact as determinants of the innovative capacity of regions, which, in turn, guides their economic growth path. Particularly, the models focus on the creation of new technological knowledge, thus neglecting the role of new organizational knowledge in explaining the assimilation of innovation at regional level. None of them consider separately the processes of knowledge creation, on the one hand, and knowledge mobilization, on the other, which severely limits the analysis of how the diverse determinants, both local and external, operate and interact to explain invention, innovation and productivity gains at regional level over time. Nonetheless, productive innovation requires two circumstances that

may or not concur locally: first, that some new knowledge become available and, second, that the production system is able to use it with productivity gains.

To overcome the analytical limitation, Vila et al (2015) propose a two-equation invention-innovation system model to represent the two inter-related processes whereby knowledge is locally created and, once available, is assimilated and transformed into efficiency gains at regional level. The system considers invention and innovation performance as connected responses, and makes explicit the difference between the explicit and the tacit forms of knowledge as impulses. The model's regional scope determines that the contextual conditions prevalent in the different regions have separate effects on regional knowledge creation, and on new knowledge assimilation. Accordingly, the external effects involved in both activities are specified as separate spatial spillovers, the one reflecting how a region's inventive performance depends on knowledge creation in other regions, and the other reflecting how the assimilation of newly available knowledge in a region depends on innovation performance in other regions. In summary, the model allows consideration of some micro-macro interfaces that influence the operation of both the invention system and the innovation system at the regional level of aggregation. Figure 2 represents the configuration of possible micro-macro interfaces in terms of influences from contextual region-specific conditions, and of spatial knowledge spillovers in a simplified two-region system of invention-innovation.

Figure 2: Micro-macro interfaces at regional level: Local contexts and spillovers.

Such a knowledge-based model of regional performance is generalized to a 17-region, 13-year panel data set to study the influence of knowledge creation and accumulation on economic efficiency at regional level in Spain between 1989 and 2001, a period of relatively high and persistent growth rates at the country level during which disparities in wellbeing widened among regions. The interfaces represented in Figure 2 by solid arrows are explicitly included for model estimation, while dotted arrows represent implicit interfaces.

GMM estimates of the two-equation dynamic system point out that the creation of technological knowledge is the result of applying local R&D effort over the stock of explicit and tacit knowledge already accumulated in the region. Local conditions, expressed as time-invariant region-specific micro-macro interfaces are relevant to explain local knowledge creation. The micro-macro interfaces of local contextual conditions on inventive performance are negative for most regions, and positive for none of them. Inventive performance of neighbor regions has a significant impact through positive micro-macro interface spillovers in the creation of explicit knowledge. Estimates also point out that efficiency gains at regional level emerge from the assimilation of newly available knowledge in the region, both in its explicit form as (lagged) inventive performance, and in its tacit form, measured in terms of increases in the average education of the labor force as a proxy for regional labor quality. Local conditions, expressed as time-invariant region-specific parameters with effects on innovation are negative for most regions, neutral for a few, and positive only for Andalusia region. Innovative performance of neighbor regions has significant impacts through positive micro-macro interface spillovers in the assimilation of explicit knowledge.

Overall estimation results from the model suggest that further advances in a region's productive efficiency would require additional effort in the creation of explicit knowledge. The creation of new explicit knowledge, in turn, depends on increased local R&D effort, the accumulation of both explicit and tacit knowledge, and improved higher education of the labor force in the region as higher education is a primary source of new organizational knowledge. Therefore, those regions that do not generate and apply new knowledge rapidly enough are at risk of being left behind in the process of economic

development, particularly on the light of the neutral or negative effects emerging from region-specific conditions. Other things being equal, the lack of a sufficient supply of highly educated workers in some regions operates as a barrier both to technological innovation and to the creation of new organizational knowledge, thus limiting the possibilities for future growth and development.

INDIVIDUAL PRODUCTIVITY, HUMAN CAPITAL AND UNIVERSITY EDUCATION

From an individual-based perspective, the volume and the composition of human capital accumulated by people determine, other things being equal, their professional quality and, consequently, influence their productive value both in pecuniary and non-pecuniary terms. The mechanisms through which individual investments in education revert to greater individual productivity have been rationalized from different perspectives. There are at least four coherent sets of reasoning that help explaining the link between education investment and productivity at the individual level. First, the original argument of human capital theory points out that education facilitates students' development of their innate talents, and provides them with abilities and professional skills, so that they will be able to produce a more valuable output, keeping constant the endowments of other productive factors (Becker, 1964). Such a higher productivity of educated people graduates is understood, therefore, as the materialization of the return to their investment in human capital through a set of acquired skills, which increase the productivity of an individual's working effort. The materialization of human capital into productivity occurs because certain abilities, which formal education is likely to perfect, allow individuals to raise the value obtained per unit of effort. The second explanation of the link between education and productivity at the individual level comes from the theory of disequilibrium (Schultz, 1975). The central idea is that those who have received a longer formal education have had the chance to develop the specific sensitivity to detect earlier any disequilibria that may occur in the markets of factor inputs and final goods. Earlier detection of disequilibria leads educated people to anticipate the changes that will occur in different markets, to recognize prematurely emerging opportunities, and to apply resources in order to take advantage. Therefore, educated individuals are better prepared to adopt novelty and to adapt their behavior to ongoing changes in ways that increase their individual productivity. The ability to recognize technological

change and to adopt new production technologies in situations of market disequilibria is, under this perspective, a direct consequence of certain specific abilities acquired within the educational system. In particular, people with greater investment in human capital are able to make decisions that are more accurate in dynamic production environments characterized by constant changes. The third line of explanation grounds on the organizational characteristics of production systems. The basic argument is that the investment in education provides people with experience in the operation of the various types of human organizations that configure the economy and govern its functioning. The very structure of educational systems, and the types of behavior that those systems require of the students during their experiences in the classroom to succeed, prepare them to function properly in the productive-entrepreneurial environment, irrespective whether they take part in it as employers, self-employed, managers or salaried workers. At university, students learn, among other things, how to respond to market signals and stimuli, and university education helps to develop personal values and norms of behavior consistent with those of the organizations that shape economies and societies, so that educated people are more productive in their economic activities. Finally, the relationship between education and individual productivity has been explained through the development of one specific key skill, the capacity for continued learning. According to this view, the future productivity of students depends more on meeting successfully the increasing demands of the education system than on the specific knowledge and intrapersonal types of behavior acquired through formal education (Carnoy and Levin, 1985). People who success in the education system have demonstrated, in multiple assessments throughout the whole length of the educational experience, their abilities to learn and to play new roles, and execute new tasks on an ongoing basis. According to this view, education improves individual productivity because the educational experience impels people to develop the specific ability to learn how to face brand new challenges by making appropriate choices and taking accurate decisions, as well as by taking on new responsibilities.

All the arguments proposed to explain the causal nexus between individual investments in university education and individual productivity suggest the presence of a diversity of components in individual human capital, although they differ in identifying which ones

are the most relevant to explain an individual's productivity. Nonetheless, the four arguments proposed to rationalize the link between university education and productivity at the individual level are not only compatible among them and with the evidence, they are definitely complementary. All of them ground on the fact that the effort dedicated to higher education determines the subsequent steps and paths of graduates within the production system. In essence, as Arrow (1997) suggested, the education experience shapes the way in which people use information to conform and recognize their preferences, to build their strategic expectations and plans, and to develop their personal decision criteria. University graduates tend to form expectations that are consistent with their preferences, to set realistic goals, and to pursue those goals more effectively and efficiently. This greater performance stems from more appropriate decision criteria that, in turn, come from a richer and sounder evaluation of the most relevant circumstances in each critical situation. Therefore, individual university graduates are more productive because they tend to obtain better results in the management of the resources available both in their professional activities and their personal life. Accordingly, university graduates will expect a greater individual share of total income as a return from the greater investment they made in terms of time and money devoted to university. Evaluations of the appropriate level of investment in formal education typically focus on market outcomes, particularly labour market monetary returns. The relationship between individual earnings and formal education has been widely studied both at the theoretical and empirical levels. The relationship is simple to state: better-educated people enjoy higher market earnings than do people with lower levels of education; earnings differentials between educational groups emerge because of differences in the levels and composition of human capital accumulated by their individual members. Human capital theory predicts that an individual's income responds to the volume of personal investment in human capital by means of formal education and professional experience. The hypothesis is expressed in the well-known quadratic earnings equation proposed by Mincer (1974), which inspires the empirical procedures most often used to estimate the productive value of individual human capital in terms of rates of return. The rate of return to university education is the discount rate where the difference between the stream of earnings for a university graduate and an otherwise comparable secondary school graduate is equal to the

stream of foregone earnings plus the direct costs of university education. The estimation of monetary returns to education generated a vast amount of literature using increasingly sophisticated methods as highlight the reviews by Card (1999) and Harmon, Oosterbeek, and Walker (2003), among many others. More recently, Dickson and Harmond (2011) identify two main trends in the recent literature on rates of return. First, the consideration of a broader concept of monetary private returns to education that takes into account earnings variability as much as average earnings, and estimates the variation in returns across the distribution of education; and second, a trend to widen the scope of non-monetary returns for the individual, and also as a means of capturing the potential social returns. As early work by Weisbrod (1964) pointed out, it is clear that traditional monetary measures do not capture all the utility-enhancing effects of university education for the individuals that complete it. Higher education provides for increased utility over time in the form of increased efficiency in a wide range of out-of-the-market activities (Haveman and Wolfe, 1984).

INDIVIDUAL UNIVERSITY GRADUATES AND THE ECONOMY

A key element to explain the role of universities for regional development from micro-economic approaches is the transformational power that higher education graduates working in a region exert locally over the economy and the society. The term transformational power here refers to the long term outcomes of a complex system of dynamic interactions that link the educational and the economic activities of individual persons within organizations, including higher education, entrepreneurship, innovation and leadership. The key question then is: why, and through what mechanisms, do HEGs contribute to transform the economy and society?. Lundvall (2008) suggests that graduates have a higher propensity to act in the economy simultaneously in the roles of equilibrators and innovators. University graduates operate as equilibrators when they perceive and react to disequilibria either in the markets of input factors or in those of final goods within the region. Early recognition of market disequilibria enables graduates to be more efficient when deciding the use of other resources, both human and material, under their command. The capacity to deal with market disequilibria is the main component of the allocative ability that is needed to evaluate accurately changing local and global economic conditions, generate comparative advantages in local

economic activities and, therefore increase productive efficiency whenever resources are reallocated to reach new equilibria. In addition, graduates contribute to regional economic development by acting as well as local innovators, i.e. when they are able to generate local market disequilibria by deliberately introducing novel ideas and knowledge in economic activities under the conditions prevalent in the local setting and within the region's environment. Lucas' (2009) microeconomic model considers change in the economy as the output of a wide class of university educated individuals whose efforts at work focus problem solving as main objective. In developed countries, the industrial revolution involved the emergence of a relatively small class of educated people whose professional efforts targeted the discovery and diffusion of new useful knowledge for practical purposes. Later, the information revolution and the democratization of higher education fostered the expansion of that knowledge-oriented minority into a rapidly widening class of people who spend their entire careers attending meetings, exchanging ideas, solving work-related problems, generating new knowledge and finding the means to apply the flow of newly generated ideas to solve new problems and face emerging challenges. In this light, productivity growth at region or country level is mainly an ongoing collective intellectual achievement, a sustained flow of new ideas to solve problems related to the production of economic output, and its distribution to satisfy human needs in the region or the country. A main feature of the model is the longitudinal and cumulative character of the learning activities of individuals and, consequently, a key point is to understand how students become graduates and undertake the transition from university education to professional activities. Figure 3 represents the transition process of an individual from pre-university education to graduate work as a chain of steps that take a number of years to complete.

Figure 3. Transition of an individual from university education to work performance

The first step involves all educational choices an individual student makes prior to enroll in university education. The economic and social background shapes both the student's system of preferences, and the limitations or constraints that apply to every educational decision, including the choice of enrolling in a particular programme at a given university. The realized choice leads the student to the second step of the transition process from education to work, that consists of the university education experience itself. University education may be regarded as a production process that combines diverse types of input factors to generate an output in the form of universities graduates. In the third step, individuals enter the labor market as university graduates, a matching process through which the needs, capacities and preferences of individual graduates confront the set of job openings available at the time within the locations where graduates search. Those job opportunities, in turn, reflect the current needs for qualified labor of firms and other work organizations operating at that time and locations. Once a graduate finds a suitable job, the fourth step of the transition process takes place as the graduate acquires job-specific work experience through learning by doing mechanisms and, in some cases, through specific on-the-job training too; clearly, this fourth step is recursive, as it happens every time graduates change jobs during their life cycle. The fifth and final step of the transition consists of the actual performance of graduates at work in a job or position, within business and other work organizations with

different orientations and goals, which are also likely to influence a graduate's work-related outcomes.

The second step of the transition deserves closer attention, since education production is a process with two types of agents involved: individual students and universities. In accordance with the literature on education production, higher education can be empirically addressed as a production process combining the educational resources supplied by higher education institutions with the personal resources of students, including their effort and dedication to study, the skills acquired before higher education, and their natural born talents (Todd and Wolpin 2003). The length and type of the study programme are predictors for the volume of the material resources available to each student. The educational resources that universities provide to students may be evaluated through monetary measures, such as yearly average expenditure per pupil, or, from a more qualitative approach, by considering the means used by universities to provide those resources to students, such as the emphasis laid on diverse teaching and learning modes during higher education. The human capital resources provided by students have two components. The first component, which is of a cumulative nature, consists of the resources applied to the education of students at all stages prior to higher education; the second component, which is contemporary with the educational experience at university, consists of the behavior developed by students during their higher education years, and can be evaluated in terms of the time and effort devoted to study. The choice of a specific functional form to connect input and output in the context of university production is relevant because it establishes restrictions on the type of analyses that can be performed and, consequently, on the scope of the conclusions and the policy implications that can be derived from them (Worthington, 2001). Stochastic frontier equations with a composite formulation of the error term allow estimation of the marginal effects of diverse input factors taken into account, and to test for the possible influence of unobserved heterogeneity among individuals due to natural ability (Aigner et al., 1977). Multilevel production functions with complex error terms emerging from several levels of observation exploit the nested nature of data (individual students within programmes, or programmes within universities) and help clarifying the marginal effects of the diverse input factors observed at different

aggregation levels (Moulton 1990), including those from individual attributes of students and from characteristics of the corresponding study programme or university

The output of a university production function consists essentially of the learning embodied in university graduates; that embodied learning may be conceptualized and measured in a wide variety of forms. Most often the output is approached in terms of academic achievement through the marks obtained by individuals when they graduate; academic results, however, are but poor predictors of graduates' subsequent economic performance. The educational credential gained by successful university students has been considered as an alternative proxy for the output of the university education production, particularly in the framework of the signaling hypothesis arguing that potential employers anticipate the market value of graduates from the type of educational credentials they hold; employers use the credentials of the applicants to a given vacancy as screening devices to reduce the costs of selection in recruiting processes. Nonetheless, employers willing to cover strategic job vacancies in their organizations are likely to be interested in the mixture of capacities or competencies possessed by the applicants. Consequently, an alternative way for conceptualizing the output of the university education production process is through the competencies developed by individual graduates after they complete their study programmes. Hartog (1992) defined competencies as those skills, talents and capabilities of people that contribute to individual and aggregate productivity gains for sustainable economic growth and development in the globalised economy. Accordingly, the competency profile of an individual at the time of graduation represents the composition of the human capital accumulated by that individual after completing university education.

Reviews of literature in both the research and policy arenas reveal that there is often little definitional and conceptual distinction between the terms competencies and skills, and that attributes often characterized as personal qualities also appear on lists of professional competencies (Weinert, 2001). There is a tendency in public discourse to use terms such as skill, qualification, ability and competency both imprecisely and interchangeably to describe what individuals must learn or be able to do in order to succeed at the workplace and in social life. The potential benefits of developing strong competency profiles for individuals entail successful participation in economic activities,

in political processes, and in social networks, meaningful interpersonal relations, and higher general job and life satisfaction (Heijke, Meng and Ramaekers, 2002; Allen and Van der Velden, 2001).

Moreover, individual competency profiles are a useful instrument to trace empirically the transmission of impulses from students' higher education experiences to subsequent graduates' work behavior and performance. The competency profile behind a given type of work-related behavior at a given time emerges as the combination of two elements: the competencies possessed by individuals at the time they graduated from university, and the competencies developed since graduation through actual professional experience. A graduate's competencies at the time of graduation express a multidimensional output of university production in terms of the composition of human capital developed by an individual. In time, those university-build capacities may develop further through learning-by-doing once graduates begin to accumulate professional work experience, which is the other main source of competencies. The ongoing, cumulative character of graduates' competency profiles highlights the relevance of initial post-graduation labor matches and earlier career steps of graduates, because some jobs and organizations provide much better chances for further competency development than other.

Within this framework, the study by Vila, Perez and Morillas (2012) proposes to identify the mechanisms that channel the contribution of higher education to the development by graduates of the competencies specifically required to innovate productively while performing their job tasks and duties. To do so, the analysis examines the relationships between the teaching and learning modes used in higher education and the level of development reported by graduates with respect to a set of professional competencies linked to innovative behaviors. West and Farr (1990) provide an operational definition of innovation as the deliberate introduction and application of new ideas, processes, products, or procedures designed to yield significant benefits for the production agent that adopts this new knowledge. The definition highlights the fact that productive innovation is a process involving a sequence of activities that individuals may undertake through their life cycle, a process that may reach their professional, economic and personal environments. Individuals seeking higher returns have good reasons to be

willing to innovate at work, that is, to take part in the development of the sequence of activities leading to the incorporation of new ideas and knowledge within their firm or organization. Accordingly, firms and other organizations that want to succeed in the knowledge economy are willing to create working environments that enhance innovative performance of employees. The sequence of activities leading to the incorporation of productive innovation includes the detection of the innovation opportunity, the proposal of new ideas and their evaluation, and, ultimately, the adoption and implementation of at least one new idea in the production process of the organization. Consequently, innovative employees must possess the capabilities necessary to be able to perform well in one or more of these activities, so the four innovation-related competences considered are the alertness to new opportunities, the ability to come up with new ideas and solutions, the willingness to question the own and others' ideas, and the ability to mobilize the capacities of others. The econometric analysis by means of stochastic frontier equations and variance components models is carried on a sample of individuals who graduated from university five years before, so their potential work experience as graduates is 60 months. Stochastic frontier equations allow control for the possible influence of unobserved heterogeneity among individuals on the output of university education expressed in terms of the acquisition of the set of competencies required to innovate at work. Variance component models, in turn, allow for the quantification of the effects on competency acquisition related to the specific study programme completed by graduates. The results illustrate that graduates' development of the competencies related to innovation depends crucially on the modes of teaching/learning they were most exposed to during their university student lives when the other relevant elements involved in the process are constant. Overall, the analysis suggests that a variety of teaching and learning modes are effective to develop diverse competencies; however, the use of proactive teaching and learning modes during higher education studies appears to promote the acquisition of innovation-related competencies differentially. Project or problem-based learning and group assignments appear as the most effective teaching methods to enhance simultaneously the development of all four innovational competencies, which suggests that facing new problems in collaboration with others is the activity that facilitates the acquisition of innovation capabilities by students. Additionally, estimates show that the influence of

higher education practice on the development of each particular competency follows a characteristic pattern, which makes it possible to identify what are the most effective teaching and learning practices for enhancing marginally the development of each one of the competencies involved in the innovation process. Accordingly, the development of the alertness to new opportunities depends mainly on the participation in research projects, the ability to come up with new ideas is developed specifically by problem-based learning, the willingness to question ideas is promoted by the emphasis made on theories and concepts, and the ability to mobilize the capabilities of others is improved specifically by using group assignments. Additionally, estimation results show that the effects of other factor inputs involved on the development of competencies are much weaker than those corresponding to higher education classroom practice. Finally, the analysis does not find evidence of unobserved individual heterogeneity influencing the acquisition of competencies in university education; however, there is evidence of a substantial influence of the type and length of the study programme on the development of some of the competencies considered, plausibly as an expression of the amount of material resources invested in university education.

At the organization level, one of the key elements to explain performance is leadership. Therefore, an interesting research question is to identify the differential characteristics of graduates who effectively lead innovation in firms and other work organizations, and to determine to what extent those characteristics can be enhanced in university education. The analysis by Davila, Mora and Vila (2014) brings together elements from leadership behavior, competency development and education production literatures to better understand why some individuals are able to lead others in work environments, and to what extent leadership competencies are developed by means of higher education and learning-by-doing on the job. The empirical work aims at three interconnected objectives. The first one is to identify the competency profile that better explains observed leadership behavior; the second objective is to explain how those specific leadership competencies have been developed; and the third objective is to examine the contribution of university education to the development of graduates' competencies for leadership. Generally speaking, theory and research on leadership behavior are based on two underlying assumptions. The first one is that the behavior of

the leader can significantly influence the performance of the other team members; the second assumption is that effective leaders are able to motivate the team to achieve relevant goals at organizational level more efficiently, thus improving both organizational and social effectiveness (Stashewsky and Koslowsky 2006; Tatum, Eberlin, Kottraba, and Bradberry 2003). The premise is that the equipment of capacities of individuals are likely to explain their relative positions and functions in professional environments and within work organizations. Therefore, individuals who lead in work organizations are characterized because their professional functions include commanding, guiding, motivating and inspiring other team members on the execution of the operations undertaken to reach expected or planned objectives of the organizational unit. To perform those functions, leaders develop a specific set of professional competencies required to deploy leadership functions, so the mechanisms involved in the process of competency development are also relevant. The competencies possessed by leaders can be seen as a specific form of individual human capital that has been developed by individuals over their lifetime. The analysis develops and connects diverse constructs, or latent variables, to explain leadership at work in terms of the professional competency of individuals and their determinants by specifying a structural equations model (SEM) with data from a sample of graduates from all study fields, as well as two subsamples of graduates from engineering and business/economics fields. The diagram in Figure 4 displays the structural equation model (SEM) proposed to connect three theory-based econometric models: a competency model for leadership derived from leadership literature; a model for competency development derived from psychometric theory; and an education production model derived from economic literature.

Figure 4. Structural equations model linking education production to leadership behavior at work five years later

The data used for the empirical analysis come from the REFLEX (The flexible professional in the knowledge society) project, a graduate survey including some 40,000 individuals of 14 countries who graduated from higher education institutions in 1999/2000 and who answered the survey questionnaire in 2005.

The relevance of the constructs formed to approximate the six hypothesized latent factors in the model and their relationships to the observed indicators were studied through a two-step data analysis procedure. In the first step, exploratory factor analysis and reliability tests were used to examine on the data the underlying dimensionality of leadership behavior, leadership competencies, and university education practice. In the second step, confirmatory factor analysis and structural equations modelling were performed to measure the proposed research models. Overall, the results indicate that all the constructs calculated from the observable variables respond adequately to the theoretical latent factors. SEM estimation results point out that there is evidence of significant direct and indirect effects of a specific competency profile for leadership regarding the three connected dimensions of leadership behavior at work proposed by Ekvall and Arvonen (1991) and Yukl, Gordon and Taber (2002), i.e., task-oriented

leadership, relations-oriented leadership and change-oriented leadership. Additionally, the results show evidence of significant direct effects of competency profiles at the time of graduation from university on individual profiles of working graduates five years later, and of specific higher education teaching and learning modes on graduates' competency profiles at the time of graduation. The model allows analysis of the influence of university classroom practice on the acquisition of diverse competencies required to lead innovation at work. The analyses identify the marginal effects of diverse teaching/learning modes, along with those of other educational and human capital input factors that enter the production function of university education. The results indicate that the panoply of teaching and learning modes deployed during university education is an essential determinant of individual progress with regard to the development of competencies required to lead human teams in working environments when the other elements involved are constant. Specifically, the findings confirm that the teaching and learning modes more intensively used during university education differentially influence the acquisition of leadership competencies. The main conclusion of the analysis is twofold. First, effective leadership can be fostered through the development by individuals of a specific set of eight competencies, which is identified. Second, those competencies behind effective leadership can be effectively enhanced through university education by using specific mixtures of pro-active teaching and learning methodologies. A stronger profile of leadership competencies at the time of graduation operates as an initial advantage in the labor market by helping graduates to make the right choices in order to find market paths that expand their own capacities to lead other people. Therefore, those graduates who were better equipped to lead at the time of graduation developed further their own leadership competencies by means of more effective learning-by-doing during their initial career stages.

Conclusion

There is a wide consensus among economists, educationalists and policy makers about the positive impacts of universities and other higher education institutions activities on economic development and human wellbeing. However, current public debates about costs and benefits of universities and their role in today's world evince that our understanding of the causal chain between university education and regional

development is rather superficial. In fact, that particular causal chain is a long and complex one because it is conformed of a number of partial impulse-response relationships where the output phenomena of a partial process enters the next partial process as an input element. Moreover, the phenomena involved as input and output in the diverse partial relationships admit conceptualizations at diverse levels of aggregation. At the aggregate level, the basic arguments typically acknowledge that universities operate as sources of human capital and generate ideas for technological progress, and that both elements –human capital and new technology- will in turn foster aggregate productivity gains for the whole economy. However, reality is far more complex than that. Micro-macro interfaces reflect the interactions that exist between the concepts and processes involved in a causal relationship or chain of relationships, and between the hypothesized causal relationships themselves, at diverse levels of aggregation. The research examples analyzed in this chapter illustrate how more or less sophisticated estimates of marginal effects of diverse input factors included in a suitable production function at a chosen level of aggregation offer a rather fragmentary picture of a complex system of interactions between impulses and responses within and across the relationships hypothesized, and within and across the levels of aggregation involved. However, such fragmentary pictures can be useful to guide the choice of appropriate instruments and methods to make explicit the presence of diverse type of micro-macro interfaces in our causal reasoning and in our empirical research. We need to learn more about the nature of those micro-macro interfaces and its effects on the trade-offs between the diverse types of resources involved, on the one hand, and between the outputs obtained, on the other, in every partial impulse-response process under analysis and for the whole causal chain between universities impulse and regional development response. The consideration of micro-macro interfaces in the analysis of the economic role of universities leads to broader views and, hopefully, to more accurate representations and model specification to generate stronger evidence. The conclusions derived from research models including explicit micro-macro interfaces are likely to be more useful for individual decision making, more relevant for university education practice, and more suitable to inform and guide effective education and policy at regional and national level.

The implementation of reforms in higher education and redesigns of local development policies should be always guided by the best evidence our understanding is able to produce. To obtain such evidence requires development of new conceptual frameworks explicitly including micro-macro interfaces and specification of empirical models able to represent coherent systems of interactions between concepts, relationships, and aggregation levels. The empirical analyses of those models should ideally involve large panel data sets from individuals, for firms and work organizations, and for regions. To obtain comprehensive and robust evidence with potential to improve the effectiveness of institutional and public interventions will require of two elements. First, we need to develop sound conceptual frameworks explicitly including micro-macro interfaces to understand better the operation of the links between the impulse of universities and the response of regional economies. Such frameworks will allow specification of empirical models able to represent coherent systems of interactions between concepts, relationships, and aggregation levels. Second, we need to deepen the analyses of the relationships between individual efforts and collective performance in every intermediate process between the initial university impulse and the desirable long term, sustainable regional development. Collaboration between researchers, universities, business and governments is crucial to increase our understanding of the dynamics between the efforts locally devoted to universities and the permanent private and social outcomes generated through them in terms of regional development and human wellbeing.

References

- Allen, J., & Van der Velden, R. (2001). Educational mismatches versus skill mismatches: effects on wages, job satisfaction, and on-the-job search. *Oxford economic papers*, 53(3), 434-452.
- Acs, Z. J., Audretsch, D. B., Braunerhjelm, P., & Carlsson, B. (2012). Growth and entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*, 39(2), 289-300.
- Bilbao-Osorio, B., & Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2004). From R&D to innovation and economic growth in the EU. *Growth and Change*, 35(4), 434-455.
- Card, D. (1999). The causal effect of education on earnings. *Handbook of labor economics*, 3, 1801-1863.

Carnoy, M., & Levin, H. (1985). *Schooling and work in the democratic state*. Stanford University Press.

Davila Quintana, C., Mora Ruiz, J. G., & E. Vila, L. (2014). Competencies which shape leadership. *International Journal of Manpower*, 35(4), 514-535.

Dickson, M., & Harmon, C. (2011). Economic returns to education: What we know, what we don't know, and where we are going—some brief pointers. *Economics of education review*, 30(6), 1118-1122.

Doyle, C., & Weale, M. (1994). Education, externalities, fertility and economic growth. *Education Economics*, 2(2), 129-167.

Ekvall, G., & Arvonen, J. (1991). Change-centered leadership: An extension of the two-dimensional model. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 7(1), 17-26.

Griliches, Z. (1979). Issues in assessing the contribution of research and development to productivity growth. *The Bell Journal of Economics*, 92-116.

Harmon, C., Oosterbeek, H., & Walker, I. (2003). The returns to education: Microeconomics. *Journal of economic surveys*, 17(2), 115-156.

Hartog, J. (1992). *Capabilities, allocation and earnings*. Kluwer: Boston.

Hartog, J. (2001). On human capital and individual capabilities. *Review of Income and Wealth*, 47(4), 515-540.

Heijke, H., Meng, C., & Ramaekers, G. (2003). An investigation into the role of human capital competences and their pay-off. *International Journal of Manpower*, 24(7), 750-773.

Knabb, S.D., & Stoddard, C. (2005). The quality of education, educational institutions, and cross-country differences in human capital accumulation. *Growth and Change*, 36(3), 354-73.

Levin, H. M., & Kelley, C. (1994). Can education do it alone?. *Economics of Education Review*, 13(2), 97-108.

Lundvall, B. A. (1992). *National systems of innovation: towards a theory of innovation and interactive learning*. London: Pinter.

Lundvall, B. A. (2008). Higher education, innovation and economic development. *Higher Education and Development*, 201-228.

Moreno, R.; Paci, R., & Usai, S. (2005). Spatial spillovers and innovation activity in European regions. *Environment and Planning A*, 37(10), 1793–1812.

Rodriguez-Pose, A. & Crescenzi, R. (2011). Research and development, spillovers, innovation systems, and the genesis of regional growth in Europe. *Regional Studies* 42(1), 51–67.

Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002–1007.

Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous technical change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), 71–102.

Škare, M. 2011. How important is human capital for growth in reforming economies?, *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*, 17(4), 667–687.

Stashewsky, S. & Koslowsky, M. (2006). Leadership team cohesiveness and team performance. *International Journal of Manpower*, 27(1), pp. 63-74.

Tatum, B.C., Eberlin, R., Kottraba, C. & Bradberry, T. (2003). Leadership, decision making, and organizational justice. *Management Decision*, 41(10), 1006-1016.

West, M.A., & Farr, J. L. (1990). Innovation at work. In M.A. West, & J. L. Farr (Eds.), *Innovation and creativity at work: Psychological and organizational strategies*. Chichester: Wiley.

Todd, P. E., & Wolpin, K. I. (2003). On the specification and estimation of the production function for cognitive achievement. *The Economic Journal*, 113(485).

Vila, L. E., Perez, P. J., & Morillas, F. G. (2012). Higher education and the development of competencies for innovation in the workplace. *Management Decision*, 50(9), 1634-1648.

Worthington, A. C. (2001). An empirical survey of frontier efficiency measurement techniques in education. *Education economics*, 9(3), 245-268.

Yukl, G., Gordon, A., & Taber, T. (2002). A hierarchical taxonomy of leadership behavior: integrating a half century of behavior research. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 9(1), pp. 15-32.